

Notes on 2D Matter Animation Program

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Abstract

The python program '2d matter animation public.py' enables an animation to be generated illustrating phase harmony in 2D for any subluminal velocity. This note documents the calculations used to generate the FR locations/phases and the SIWF wave fronts.

1 FR Locations and Phases

The animation always begins with FRs at position $x = 0$ (all y 's) having phase 0, i.e. with phase arrow pointing right. The locations of other locations of FRs along the x axis (the direction of motion) at $t = 0$ are given by multiplying integer x values by κ where

$$\kappa = \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_F^2}{c^2}}$$

and V_F is the velocity of the structure. Subsequent locations of FRs are calculated by moving the initial positions to the right at velocity V_F . The phases of the FRs at the displaced positions and at times $t > 0$ are calculated from the SIWF p sinusoid:

$$\phi_p = \frac{\omega_0 V_F}{\kappa c^2} x - \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} t + \phi_{t=0, x=0}$$

The initial phase at $t = 0, x = 0$ has been set to zero so:

$$\phi_p = \frac{\omega_0 V_F}{\kappa c^2} x - \frac{\omega_0}{\kappa} t$$

The time dilation of the FR's rotation rate is inherent in the p sinusoid.

2 Illustration of the 4 Component SIWF Waves

The animation is intended to illustrate phase harmony of the FRs with the physical SIWF waves moving at velocity c . There are four such waves, say: Forward, Backward, Up (i.e. $+y$) and down (i.e. $-y$). The method chosen to illustrate these is to identify a single crest (i.e. with phase 0) for each wave. There are obviously many such crests separated by unit distance in their direction of motion but presenting them all makes the animation too busy.

2.1 The Forward Wave (Red)

The Forward wave is trivial as it starts on the y axis at $x = 0$ and moves at velocity c to the right.

2.2 The Backward Wave Initial location (Blue)

This is not trivial, since at $t = 0$ there might not be any FRs with the correct phase along the x axis. The location of the n th FR along the row at time zero is

$$n\kappa$$

Thereafter it moves right with velocity V_F so its location at time t is given by

$$x_{n,t} = n\kappa + V_F t$$

Let the equation of motion for the blue line be

$$x_{b,t} = x_{b,0} - tc$$

Calling the point in space-time where the crest line meets an FR the "appointment", equating the x locations gives the appointment time t_a .

$$n\kappa + V_F t_a = x_{b,0} - t_a c$$

$c = 1$ so

$$\begin{aligned} V_F t_a + t_a &= x_{b,0} - n\kappa \\ t_a &= \frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Back substituting to obtain x_a

$$x_a = n\kappa + V_F \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) \quad (2)$$

Now we require that at the appointment, the phase is π . The phase equation is

$$\phi_p = \frac{\omega_0 V x}{\kappa c^2} - \frac{\omega_0 t}{\kappa} + \phi_{t=0, x=0}$$

The initial phase at $x = 0$; $t = 0$ is 0 and we require the phase to be π so

$$\pi = \frac{2\pi V_F x}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t}{\kappa}$$

Substituting the appointment details Eq 1 and Eq 2 gives

$$\pi = \frac{2\pi V_F}{\kappa} \left(n\kappa + V_F \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) \right) - \frac{2\pi}{\kappa} \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right)$$

π cancels and multiply through by κ

$$\kappa = 2V_F \left(n\kappa + V_F \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) \right) - 2 \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right)$$

Expand

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa &= 2V_F n\kappa + 2V_F^2 \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) - 2 \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) \\ \kappa - 2V_F n\kappa &= \left(\frac{x_{b,0} - n\kappa}{V_F + 1} \right) (2V_F^2 - 2) \\ \frac{(\kappa - 2V_F n\kappa)(V_F + 1)}{2V_F^2 - 2} &= x_{b,0} - n\kappa \\ \frac{(\kappa/2 - V_F n\kappa)(V_F + 1)}{V_F^2 - 1} &= x_{b,0} - n\kappa \\ \frac{(\kappa/2 - V_F n\kappa)(V_F + 1)}{(V_F - 1)(V_F + 1)} &= x_{b,0} - n\kappa \\ \frac{(\kappa/2 - V_F n\kappa)}{(V_F - 1)} &= x_{b,0} - n\kappa \end{aligned}$$

Rearrange

$$\begin{aligned} x_{b,0} &= \frac{(\kappa/2 - V_F n\kappa)}{(V_F - 1)} + n\kappa \\ x_{b,0} &= \frac{\kappa/2 - V_F n\kappa - n\kappa + V_F n\kappa}{(V_F - 1)} \\ x_{b,0} &= \frac{\kappa/2 - n\kappa}{(V_F - 1)} \\ x_{b,0} &= \frac{\kappa}{(1 - V_F)} (n - 1/2) \end{aligned}$$

This is the position of the vertical blue line at $t = 0$ which ensures it will meet all the FRs with the correct phase (identified as `blue_start` in the function `get_offsets`).

3 Slope of the Transverse Harmony waves for Spin Down Matter

Phase harmony of the transverse waves can only be maintained if they are sloping i.e. have components in the y and x directions. The slope is calculated by reference to Figure 1. The left hand two phase arrows represent the situation at the initial time, whilst the right hand ones are one period T later. α is the

Figure 1: Calculating the slope of the transverse wavefront

required angle. The FRs have travelled $V_F T$ in one period; whilst the SIWF wave has travelled cT . By inspection, we have $\sin \alpha = \frac{V_F T}{cT}$ so

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{V_F}{c}$$

Although it is not used in the animation, we can also use Figure 1 to calculate the components of the wave vector. The distance cT contains 2π radians of phase. But in general, $T = 2\pi/\omega$ and here we have $\omega = \omega_0 \kappa$. So

$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0 \kappa}$$

This distance has 2π radians of phase so

$$\|k\| = \frac{2\pi\omega_0 \kappa}{2\pi c}$$

$$\|k\| = \frac{\omega_0 \kappa}{c}$$

Now use the direction to find k_x and k_y . For a southbound wave we have a positive slope for the wavefront and

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{V_F}{c}$$

k_x is positive and k_y is negative. Also,

$$\frac{\|k_x\|}{\|k\|} = \sin \alpha; \quad \frac{\|k_y\|}{\|k\|} = \cos \alpha$$

$$\|k_x\| = \|k\| \frac{V_F}{c}$$

Substitute for $\|k\|$

$$\|k_x\| = \frac{\omega_0 \kappa V_F}{c^2}$$

Now use Pythagoras

$$\begin{aligned} \|k_y\|^2 &= \|k\|^2 - \|k_x\|^2 \\ \|k_y\|^2 &= \frac{\omega_0^2 \kappa^2}{c^2} - \frac{\omega_0^2 \kappa^2 V_F^2}{c^4} \\ k_y^2 &= \frac{\omega_0^2 \kappa^2}{c^2} \left(1 - \frac{V_F^2}{c^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

But $1 - \frac{V_F^2}{c^2}$ is κ^2 so

$$\begin{aligned} \|k_y\|^2 &= \frac{\omega_0^2 \kappa^4}{c^2} \\ \|k_y\| &= \pm \frac{\omega_0 \kappa^2}{c} \end{aligned}$$

For a southbound transverse wave k_y is negative. So

$$k_x = \frac{\omega_0 \kappa V_F}{c^2} \hat{x}; \quad k_y = -\frac{\omega_0 \kappa^2}{c} \hat{y}$$

where \hat{x} and \hat{y} are unit vectors in x and y .

4 Offset for the Transverse Waves for Spin Down Matter

- For the green line:

The phase wave is

$$\phi_p = \frac{\omega_0 V x}{\kappa c^2} - \frac{\omega_0 t}{\kappa} + \phi_{t=0, x=0}$$

Phase at $t = 0; x = 0$ is 0 and $c = 1; \omega_0 = 2\pi$

$$\phi_p = \frac{2\pi V_F x}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t}{\kappa}$$

Want appointment when

$$\phi = \alpha - \pi/2$$

From Eq ?? $\alpha = \arcsin(V_F)$

$$\arcsin(V_F) - \frac{\pi}{2} = \frac{2\pi V_F x}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t}{\kappa}$$

As it starts from the x origin the location of the FR is given by

$$x(t) = V_F t$$

$$\arcsin(V_F) - \frac{\pi}{2} = \frac{2\pi V_F V_F t_a}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t_a}{\kappa}$$

$$\arcsin(V_F) - \frac{\pi}{2} = \frac{2\pi}{\kappa} t_a (V_F^2 - 1)$$

$$t_a = \left(\arcsin(V_F) - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \frac{\kappa}{2\pi (V_F^2 - 1)}$$

Factor out -1 from both bracketed terms and cancel.

$$t_a = \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin(V_F) \right) \frac{\kappa}{2\pi (1 - V_F^2)}$$

But $1 - V_F^2 = \kappa^2$ so

$$t_a = \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin(V_F) \right) \frac{1}{2\pi\kappa}$$

x location of appointment

$$x_a = V_F t_a$$

$$x_a = \frac{V_F}{2\pi\kappa} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin(V_F) \right)$$

For the y offset, take the appointment x and back off in y the distance $t_a v_y$ where v_y is y component of the velocity of the line

$$v_y = \frac{1}{\cos(\arctan(V_F/\kappa))}$$

which simplifies to

$$v_y = \frac{1}{\kappa}$$

$$t v_y = \frac{1}{2\pi\kappa} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin(V_F) \right) \frac{1}{\kappa}$$

which is the form used in the program, displaced in integer values of y to ensure it is in a reasonable starting position on the animation. Sanity check: when $V_F = 0$ the y offset is $1/4$ as required. So put the starting point at x_a and y at this offset plus whatever integer you like. and construct a line having the required slope.

- For the yellow line a similar process is used. The phase wave is

$$\phi_p = \frac{\omega_0 V x}{\kappa c^2} - \frac{\omega_0 t}{\kappa} + \phi_{t=0, x=0}$$

Phase at $t = 0; x = 0$ is 0 and $c = 1; \omega_0 = 2\pi$

$$\phi_p = \frac{2\pi V_F x}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t}{\kappa}$$

Want appointment when:

$$\phi = -(3\pi/2 + \alpha)$$

Minus because this is spin down and the rotation is in the negative sense mathematically. Strictly speaking α is negative but From Eq ??

$$\alpha = \arcsin(V_F)$$

and it will be given as positive.

$$-\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) = \frac{2\pi V_F x}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t}{\kappa}$$

As it starts from the x origin location of the FR is given by

$$x(t) = V_F t$$

$$-\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) = \frac{2\pi V_F V_F t_a}{\kappa} - \frac{2\pi t_a}{\kappa}$$

$$-\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) = \frac{2\pi}{\kappa} t_a (V_F^2 - 1)$$

$$t_a = -\left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) \frac{\kappa}{2\pi (V_F^2 - 1)}$$

Extract and cancel factor of -1

$$t_a = \left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) \frac{\kappa}{2\pi (1 - V_F^2)}$$

But $1 - V_F^2 = \kappa^2$ so

$$t_a = \left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right) \frac{1}{2\pi \kappa}$$

$$x_a = V_F t_a$$

$$x_a = \frac{V_F}{2\pi \kappa} \left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F)\right)$$

For the y offset, take the appointment x and back off in y the distance $-t_a v_y$ where v_y is the velocity of the line

$$v_y = \frac{1}{\kappa}$$

$$t v_y = \frac{-1}{2\pi\kappa} \left(\frac{3\pi}{2} + \arcsin(V_F) \right) \frac{1}{\kappa}$$

Sanity check: when $V_F = 0$ the y offset is $-3/4$ as required. So put the starting point at x_a and y at this offset plus whatever integer is needed.